

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D5.10 Report on standardisation & spectrum allocation recommendations

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Responsible Author	Tanel Jairus (TTU)		
Contributors	Arvi Sadam (EEE), Johan Scholliers (VTT), Tanel Jairus (TTU), Duc Pham-Minh (ADSF)		
Peer reviewer	George Agapiou (WINGS) Priit Roosipuu (TTU) David Quesada (ENIDE)		

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	The 3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G-AA	5G Automotive Association
5GPPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CEN	The European Committee for Standardization
CSP	CAM Standardisation Plan
ETSI	The European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
IEEE SA	The Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Standards Association
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
ISO	The International Organization for Standardization
ITU-T	International Telegraph Union Telecommunication Standardization Sector
NGMN	The Next Generation Mobile Networks Alliance
ONF	The Open Networking Foundation
SDOs	Standards Developing Organisations
gNB	Next-Generation Node B
IAB	Integrated Access Backhaul
MFCN	Mobile and Fixed Communications Networks
TDD	Time Duplex

Executive Summary

The 5G-ROUTES project has concluded its mission to accelerate the acceptance of Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM), paving the way for fully autonomous, safer, cleaner, more traffic-efficient, user-friendly, and reliable mobility across Europe. This report serves crucial component of the project's final documentation, summarising achievements in standardisation activities, spectrum allocation recommendations, and insights gained from real-world trials. In light of the changes to the project objectives, the focus of this task has shifted towards maritime environments.

The maritime trials conducted by 5G-ROUTES have opened new pathways for extending CAM services to maritime environments, demonstrating the potential of multi-hop communication while highlighting challenges related to maintaining low latency and managing bandwidth limitations.

Key technical enablers developed and validated during the project include:

1. Maritime Multi-hop Communication systems
2. Hybrid Network Integration techniques
3. Dynamic Spectrum Management methods

The project's standardisation activities have made significant contributions in several areas:

1. The Cross-Administrative Domain Integration Fabric, expanding the ETSI ZSM framework
2. The CAM Repository, simplifying multi-domain CAM service deployment
3. V2X Message Routing via MEC, advancing ETSI efforts in this area
4. Identification of gaps in security standards for CAM in MEC environments

The project's spectrum allocation recommendations aim to create a flexible and efficient spectrum environment supporting diverse CAM services across the EU, including maritime applications. Proposals for cross-border operations address critical challenges in ensuring seamless CAM services across national boundaries.

5G-ROUTES has made substantial contributions to the CAM landscape, providing practical, implementable proposals based on rigorous research and real-world trials. These proposals, if adopted, have the potential to significantly accelerate the deployment of CAM services across Europe, fostering a more connected, efficient, and sustainable transportation future.

This report details the project's findings, recommendations, and future directions, providing valuable insights for researchers, industry stakeholders, policymakers, and standardisation bodies working towards the realisation of advanced CAM services.

1 Introduction

1.1 Mapping 5G ROUTES Outputs

The vision of 5G-ROUTES is to support the EU in achieving its goal of becoming a world leader in Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM), by accelerating the acceptance of fully autonomous, safer, cleaner, more traffic efficient, more user friendly and reliable mobility, as well as for seamless and uninterrupted delivery of interoperable cross-border CAM services along main transport paths throughout Europe.

This document, D5.10, represents the final output of 5G-ROUTES activities related to standardisation aspects and spectrum allocation recommendations. It builds upon and expands the initial work presented in D5.9. Since the submission of D5.9, the project has made substantial progress in its research, trials, and analysis, with a particular focus on maritime applications of CAM.

One of the key aspects identified as necessary to efficiently fulfil the project's vision is the contribution to the specification and adoption of common standards. Given the substantial infrastructure investments required for the transition to 5G, the existence of a clear and consolidated standards ecosystem represents a solid foundation for fostering the long-term provision of 5G-enabled services in the market.

5G-ROUTES has aimed to support and contribute to the EU vision through the alignment of its development with existing standards, the identification of standardisation gaps, and the contribution to further development of relevant standards. The project has promoted a proactive and joint approach through consortium partners, members of pre-standardisation bodies and fora (e.g., 5GPPP, 5G-AA, IETF, NGMN, UIC) and Standards Developing Organisations (SDOs), such as 3GPP, ITU-T, IEEE SA, ETSI, CEN, ISO, and ONF.

Table 1 Adherence to 5G ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G ROUTES GA Component Title	5G ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D5.10 Report on standardisation activities and spectrum allocation recommendations	Report on standardisation activities and spectrum allocation recommendations	Updated chapters of D5.9 and additional chapters of the deliverable	<i>Chapters 3, 4 and 5 define the standardisation objectives of the project and associated methodology expanding on D5.9.</i>
TASKS			
T5.4 Standardisation contribution and spectrum allocation recommendations	<i>5GROUTES will use standardisation to exploit the impacts of the project result and to most efficiently invest the public funding of this project. It will go about this in two ways: Firstly, it will ensure that the R&I</i>	Chapters 3 to 7	<i>Chapter 3 identifies relevant standardisation bodies. Chapter 4 describes the contributions. Chapter 5 provides the spectrum allocation recommendations. Chapter 6 explains the cross-border coordination. Chapter 7 describes the results of maritime trials.</i>

	<p><i>results produced by the project will be aligned with existing and emerging standards from the relevant standardisation bodies (e.g. 3GPP, ETSI, ITU, IEEE, IETF, etc.). Secondly, through 5G-PPP pre-standardisation WG and contributing to the 2nd phase of 5G standardisation efforts, 5G-ROUTES will analyse the standardisation gaps with respect to the 5G-PPP vision so that such gaps can be adequately addressed.</i></p>		
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1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This document addresses the standardisation activities of the 5G ROUTES project.

- Chapter 2 expands on the CAM technical enablers identified in D5.9 and revises the role of 5G for CAM services, with a particular focus on maritime applications. It includes the updated list of relevant SDOs and standardisation interest groups provided in D5.9.
- Chapter 3 describes the project's contributions to the standards. This chapter expands on the initial plans outlined in D5.9, incorporating the outcomes of the project's standardisation activities.
- Chapter 5 describes the recommendations for spectrum allocation.
- Chapter 4 investigates the spectrum allocation specificities and provides updated recommendations to address such challenges, particularly in the context of cross-border and maritime CAM services. It builds upon the initial recommendations provided in D5.9, incorporating new insights from the project's research and trials.
- Chapter 6 presents the results of the maritime trials conducted by the project. This chapter details the unique challenges and opportunities identified in extending CAM services to maritime environments.

2 State of the art and technical enablers

This chapter expands on the D5.9 findings regarding the overview of Connected and automated mobility (CAM) technical enablers, relevant SDOs and standardisation interest group and provides the state of the art of CAM and associated technical enablers. This chapter also updates the gap analysis between 5G-ROUTES ambitions and actual standards.

2.1 5G and CAM

In D5.9, Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) was described as an ecosystem of technologies addressing connectivity on mobile platforms for various services, including automated driving and vehicle controls. The report emphasized the need for collaboration among stakeholders such as telecommunications manufacturers, network operators, and service providers.

Key CAM requirements identified included global service area coverage, high system capacity, increased throughput, ultra-low latency, high reliability, flexibility, and interoperability. The report highlighted 5G as a crucial enabler for CAM, capable of meeting these requirements through its ability to offer massive Machine Type Communications, Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications, and extreme Mobile Broadband services simultaneously.

Technical enablers for CAM were identified, including edge computing, session/service continuity, MEC-5G-NFV management and orchestration, QoS prediction, and V2X message routing. The role of standardization was emphasized as critical for ensuring interoperability, defining common rules, and addressing various aspects such as V2X protocols, 5G network requirements, and spectrum harmonization.

The report also touched on the importance of regulatory frameworks and safety norms in the development of CAM services, highlighting the need for standards to evolve to accommodate the advanced capabilities of new technologies while ensuring system coexistence and safety.

2.2 Identification of SDOs

Table 2 List of relevant organizations

Standards body, forum	Specific group targeted	Main contributors	5G-ROUTES contribution	WP to impact
Pre-Standardisation				
5G-PPP	Pre-standardisation	CTTC ADSF, EEE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitor current activities on behalf of the consortium, align project's outcomes into work for next releases (e.g. R.18) 	WP1- WP4
5G-AA	WG2, WG4	ADSF, EEE, VED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WG2: Define interoperable solutions for CAM architecture WG4: Spectrum requirements for V2X in ITS 	WP2
IETF	ANIMA SFC ACTN	EEE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ANIMA: common Autonomic Network control plane elements related to specific requirements of E2E 5G networks SFC, ACTN: model transformations and test applicability of developed solutions/standards 	WP2- WP3
NGNM	Management, Orchestration,	EEE ADSF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requirements for unified operation and management of cross border 5G 	WP2- WP3

	Sat integration		networks (e.g. resource reservation & distribution) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of satellite solutions in 5G terrestrial ecosystem 		
UIC, EIM	FRMCS	EVR PV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leverage findings from UC5.3 trials to progress work in FRMCS including the support of multiple access technologies 	WP4	
Standards Developing Organisations					
3GPP	SA1&2, SA4&5, CT1, CT3, CT4, RAN1, RAN3	CTTC EEE, ADSF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overall system requirements and dynamic network slicing. Different functional splits for fronthaul in the RAN WG. 5G management and 5G edge cloud services w.r.t MEC Satellite integration with the 5G core network and satellite / terrestrial handovers 	WP1 WP3 WP4	
ITU-T	ITU-T 2020 FG, FG NET-2030	EEE, ADSF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vision, novel use cases and architecture for Net 2030 Conformance of ML functionalities in 5G networks 	WP2	
IEEE SA	SDN/NFV, SLAs	CTTC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse and present potential contributions to IEE P1917.1 for improving reliability, analytics and requirements for SDN/NFV 	WP2	
	Green ICT	TTU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reporting activities/innovations related to the 5G base-stations energy efficiency (waveforms vs power amplifier) 	WP3	
ETSI	ZSM ISG	CTTC, IQU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End-to-end network slicing Dynamic on the fly network slicing 	WP2	
	ITS	VTT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report findings from 5G-ROUTES trials to the automotive Intelligent Transport Systems WG for different V2X scenarios. 	WP4	
	ENI	WINGS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitor and report on project's outcomes related to network intelligence functionalities 	WP2	
	NFV		WINGS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring and reporting on project's NFV-related aspects 	WP2
			CTTC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NFV and service orchestration for cross domain CAM services, fusing project outcomes into work for next releases 	WP2
			ATOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thanks to its role in the OSM Technical Steering Committee, Atos will facilitate any relevant contribution to OSM 	
	MEC ISG	CTTC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Content caching techniques leveraging ML algorithms 	WP2	
	RRS	WINGS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring and reporting on project's innovative radio usage 	WP2	
TC RT	EVR, PV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interoperability requirements for ITS and urban rail apps 	WP3		
CEN	TC 278	VTT		WP4	

ISO	TC 204	VED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use findings from 5G-ROUTES field trials for progression on the work in urban intelligent transport systems (ITS), mobility, vehicle/roadway warning and control systems. 	
ONF	T&I WG	CTTC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuously reporting the activities/innovations of the project to the Testing & Interoperability Working Group 	WP1 WP4
IHO	S-123	EEE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experts from 5GROUTES had multiple meetings with IHO S-123 to discuss the suitable set of network parameters to describe cellular network quality in close-to-shore areas. 	WP4

2.3 Gap analysis

This section expands on the gap analysis provided in D5.9, reflecting the latest developments in the field. ETSI is currently working on ETSI TR 102 962, titled “Framework for Public Mobile Networks in Cooperative ITS (C-ITS)” (ETSI TR 102 962, 2012), aimed at deploying C-ITS applications (ETSI Release 1 and release 2) using the 3GPP Uu interface. The document describes the information architecture for the delivery of Day 1 and Day 2 services. Additionally, ETSI TR 102 9693, is currently under revision, and describes how cellular infrastructure can be used to provide C-ITS services. The suggested approach, adopted by the C-ROADS platform, involves connecting vehicle OBUs to a backend, which exchanges the information with other backends and the vehicle OBUs attached to them.

ETSI is advancing Release 2 of the C-ITS standards. Whereas Release 1 focused on Day 1 services and ITS-G5, Release 2 aims to adopt a more technology-agnostic approach. A limitation of Release 1 is its failure to follow the OSI approach, leading to mixed layers. A specific issue is Geonet working, which is essential for distribution of messages in the neighbourhood of the vehicles, but which is not necessary for network communications; it is included in the IEEE1609.2 security header. In Release 2, the interdependence of standards is attempted to be kept to a minimum.

Release 2 introduces also new messages, including the CPM (Collective Perception Message) and MCM (Manoeuvre Coordination Message). CPMs are used in the 5G-ROUTES project: the messages used are based on ETSI TR 103 562. During the project, this standard was updated to TS 103 324; however, to avoid interoperability issues, the previously agreed version was kept. ETSI continues to work on optimising CPMs, aiming to reduce the size of the messages by deciding the objects which should be transmitted, without losing essential information.

The ETSI ITS standards do not currently incorporate 5G-specific elements, such as Multi-Access Edge Computing and network slicing. Regarding MEC, ETSI GS MEC 030 V2.1.1 “Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC); V2X Information Service API” (GS MEC 030, 2020) specifies how V2X messages can be routed over MECs to reduce latency, but the content of these messages is outside the scope of the standard. There is currently no linkage between the MEC standard and the C-ITS standards mentioned above.

Hence, regarding CCAM standardisation, the following issues are still under development:

- Specification of ETSI release 2 messages: including the MCM
- Standardisation of the information architecture ((ETSI TR 102 962, 2012)): MEC should be incorporated in the standard. Standardisation of the information protocols, e.g. for communication between vehicle and network (e.g. MQTT) and the protocols for communication between MECs or service backend

- Security related standardisation: includes the signing of the messages and misbehaviour detection.
- 5G cross-border roaming: Simple inter-MNO and multi-MNO roaming is still under discussion in 3GPP
- Network slicing: a key feature of 5G technology in V2X scenarios (3GPP TS 22.186 (TS 22.186 , 2017), 3GPP TS 23.501 (TS 23.501, 2018), 3GPP TS 23.287 (TS 23.287, 2020)) and 5GROUTES must make sure we have the necessary support for the selected use-cases
- Network based positioning. Positioning services description and requirements are specified in TS 22.261 (TS 22.261, 2020) and TS 22.186 (TS 22.186 , 2017). There are several methods for positioning with different accuracy levels. 5G-ROUTES must make sure we have the necessary support for the selected use-cases.
- Civilian-Military Spectrum Sharing: Spectrum sharing between civilian and military networks presents both challenges and opportunities. The need for standardized protocols to manage dynamic spectrum access is growing, especially in urban areas where spectrum is scarce. Developing mechanisms for priority-based spectrum sharing will be critical for ensuring that both sectors can coexist without interference.
- Remote Interference Coordination Frameworks for Cross-border Coordination: The deployment of 5G networks across cross-border regions presents significant challenges in managing radio interference between neighbouring countries.

3 Standardisation activities

As it has been presented in the deliverable D5.9, 5G-ROUTES has followed a specific approach to ensure the alignment of the 5G-ROUTES research with the existing standards. Therefore, this chapter is focusing on reporting on the standardisation activities, and the standardisation roadmap to track the evolution of the relevant standards and the 5G-ROUTES plants to contribute to the specifications if necessary.

5G-ROUTES followed the principle, where the research activities conducted within the project align where possible with existing relevant standards and where possible 5G-ROUTES will aim to contribute to the evolution of the standards relevant to the CAM and identified key technical enablers. The identified standardisation organisations and working groups were tracked in their evolution for the alignment of 5G-ROUTES development with relevant standards and to contribute to the specification of their next versions.

5G-ROUTES had a wide area to consider for such approach, including the CAM's specialized organisations (C-ROADS, ETSI ITS), the 5G standards organisations (3GPP) and the wider communication standardisation vision uniformed at European level (5GPP).

Figure 1: 5G-ROUTES relation

During the project, 5G-ROUTES standardisation activities conducted are further detailed in the following section.

3.1 The 5G-ROUTES Cross-Administrative Domain Integration Fabric

The design of the IF enabler developed by CTTC is based on the guidelines encountered in the architectural framework defined by ETSI Zero Touch and Network Service Management (ZSM) [10]. Such design expands the scope of ETSI ZSM, which only relates to the interaction within different segments of the same AD but does not tackle relations across independent ADs, implying the communication across different instances of the IF.

3.2 The 5G-ROUTES CAM Repository

In order to manage the deployment of CAM services in the PoP of the field trial, the components that participate in the E2E service orchestration need access to the NFV descriptors (compliant with ETSI data models SOL 006 and package specifications, SOL 004 and SOL 007 and a cohesive inventory with the inner Helm charts and dockers images that are referenced in the KNFs (UC artefacts). According to the architecture of the project, 5G-ROUTES plans to instantiate the entire stack of enablers at each administrative domain following a cross-domain management based on ETSI ZSM guidelines. This requires a synchronisation mechanism for UC artefacts between the local domain where the UC starts and the neighbour domain where the CAM Service will be instantiated when the user moves as part of the seamless cross-border mechanism offered by 5G-ROUTES. This will be addressed by the CAM Repository and will greatly simplify the UC preparation phase since it will allow UC developers to provision a multi-domain scenario in a single action regardless of the domain where they are initially connected. This will save a great deal of effort since UCs will not need to distribute their network service descriptors and images to all the infrastructures where their CAM Service may be required during each execution.

3.3 V2X Message Routing via MEC

The V2X Message Routing via MEC, which is developed in 5G-ROUTES, builds on the work from previous projects, such as CONCORDA [7], and 5G-MOBIX. [8]. Standardised V2X messages are transmitted over MQTT, and the geographical distribution of messages is based on quadtrees. This approach is also mentioned in the draft of ETSI TR 102 962, which is currently under work.

The method for communication between the two instances in the different domains is based on the approach of the C-ROADS platform for the communication between ITS backends, which is based on AMQP.

The use of MEC for transmitting V2X is also addressed by the current draft of ETSI TR 102 962 in TC ITS, and by the Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) ETSI Industry Specification Group (ISG), which produced ETSI GR MEC 022 and GR MEC 030. 5GAA has tested the operation of V2X message exchange in a multi-vendor multi-MNO environment using MECs in the MEC4AUTO project.

When going forward to a deployable version of the message routing enabler, also message security should be considered. C-ITS refer to intelligent transport systems that enable ITS users to interact and cooperate by exchanging secured and trusted messages, without any prior knowledge of each other and in a non-discriminatory manner. Hence, C-ITS refers to secured and trusted V2X messages. To ensure that C-ITS messages can be trusted, a common C-ITS Trust model has been created by the European Commission. The C-ITS trust model is implemented by means of a policy on the use of PKI (Public Key Infrastructure), called the EU CCMS (European Union C-ITS Security Credential Management System). C-ITS messages are standardized by ISO and ETSI and are signed according to ETSI TS 103 097. Messages are transmitted by ITS Stations, either Vehicle ITS stations, Roadside ITS stations or Central ITS stations. The requirements for ITS stations and operators are set up in the EU C-ITS Security [9] and Certificate Policy [10]. Requirements include for instance that ITS Stations have to be designed, developed, and assessed so that they meet the specifications. The stations have to be assessed by a SOG-IS recognized test lab and certified using security assessment criteria against a certified protection profile, as specified in Common Criteria (ISO 15408). Protection profiles have recently been generated for Vehicle ITS stations and roadside ITS stations. However, a protection profile for central ITS stations (e.g. C-ITS backend) has not yet been developed. The development of a protection profile for central ITS station is expected to be provided by the C-ROADS platform. Open questions relate e.g. to the HSM, as a physical HSM is required by the current ETSI standards. The use of a V2X broker and V2X services in a MEC environment have currently to take these requirements into account. The current C-ITS requirements make it not possible to have CAM services and enablers, which generate V2X messages, certified as ITS stations, and hence to become part of the C-ITS trust model.

Standardisation work needs to be performed both on agreeing on the protocols for message exchange, but the major challenges are related to the standardisation of solutions for ensuring the security and allowing V2X enablers and services to become part of C-ITS deployments.

4 Spectrum Allocation Recommendations

This chapter expands on D5.9 regarding the spectrum allocation specificities and recommendations to address such challenges, particularly in the context of cross-border CAM services.

4.1 The 5G-NR Bands and Coverage

The frequencies considered by the ITU during the latest World Radiocommunication Conference (WRC-19) for 5G systems are:

- 24.25-27.5 GHz
- 37-43.5 GHz
- 45.5-47 GHz
- 47.2-48.2 GHz
- 66-71 GHz

These are in addition to current 2G-4G bands. In total, 17.25 GHz of spectrum has been identified for IMT by the Conference, compared with 1.9 GHz of bandwidth available before WRC-19. Out of this, 14.75 GHz of spectrum has been harmonized worldwide, reaching 85% of global harmonisation (ITU, 2020).

For CAM services, particularly in cross-border contexts, harmonisation needs to reach near 100% to ensure service continuity and efficient operations. Furthermore, while coverage has been traditionally specified in terms of population percentage, for CAM services, coverage needs to be evaluated in terms of area or roads and rails infrastructure.

4.2 The European Union 5G and CAM Initiatives

The EU has adopted several initiatives regarding 5G and CAM, as described in 5G-ROUTES deliverable D1.3, Chapter 5, Section 5.2 "CAM legislative framework". These initiatives outline the steps towards the deployment of automated driving in the EU and provide a framework for the development of CAM services.

4.3 Current Status of Radio Spectrum and Regulation in 5G-ROUTES Trial Countries

The current situation in the countries where the 5G-ROUTES project trials take place (Latvia, Estonia, and Finland) is described in 5G-ROUTES deliverable D1.3, Chapter 5, Section 5.1 "Spectrum regulation and availability". This section details how the spectrum is regulated and what the availability is in those countries, how coordination between neighboring countries takes place, and what the challenges are.

The use of frequencies in the border area shall be determined by bilateral and trilateral cross-border frequency coordination agreements. Agreements with neighbouring countries are concluded with a view to agreeing the conditions for the use of frequencies in the border area and the principles of frequency coordination, which ensure the use of frequencies without harmful interference from neighbouring countries, as well as facilitate the coordination of frequencies with neighbouring countries. These arrangements shall provide for the level of emission permitted in the direction of the neighbouring countries concerned and for other conditions and shall specify the cases in which prior coordination of the base stations to be installed with the neighbouring country is to be carried out. In cases where there is no international frequency coordination agreement on conditions for the use of frequencies in the border area,

countries shall be guided by the Rules of Procedure of ITU Radio and shall use the relevant CEPT recommendations to address technical issues. [11]

According to Radio Regulations, in radio region 1 of the International Telecommunications Union (ITU), which includes Latvia and neighbouring countries, the mobile radio service in the radio frequency band 3400-3600 MHz has primary status and the band is also allocated to international mobile telecommunications (IMT). On the other hand, in the 3600-3800 MHz radio frequency band in the ITU Radio 1 region, the mobile radio service has secondary status. Secondary service radio stations shall not cause harmful radio interference to existing or planned primary service radio stations and shall not require protection of radio stations from harmful radio interference. [11]

Applicable technical conditions and restrictions for the use of the radio frequency band 3400-3800 MHz for mobile and fixed communications networks (MFCN) time duplex (TDD) systems:

Table 3 Frequency coordination between neighbouring countries [11]

Area	3400-3600 MHz	3600-3800 MHz
Border area with Russia	<p>The power flow density generated by THE MFCN station shall not exceed – 154.5 dB (W/(m² × 4 kHz) (or 22,3 dB μ V/m/5 MHz) at the 3 m State border.</p> <p>The calculation shall be based on ITU-R recommendation P.452-16 at 20% of the time, with Smooth Earth terrain profile</p>	<p>Use under protected conditions:</p> <p>The power flow density generated by THE MFCN station shall not exceed – 139,8 dB (W/(m² × 1 MHz) (or 13 dB μ V/m/5 MHz) at the limit of 20 m.</p> <p>The calculation shall be based on ITU-R recommendation P.452-16 at 1% of the time, with Smooth Earth terrain profile.</p> <p>Use under vulnerable conditions*:</p> <p>The power flow density generated by THE MFCN station shall not exceed – 154.5 dB (W/(m² × 4 kHz) (or 22,3 dB μ V/m/5 MHz) at the 3 m State border.</p> <p>The calculation shall be based on ITU-R recommendation P.452-16 at 20% of the time, with Smooth Earth terrain profile.</p> <p>* Secondary service radio stations shall not cause harmful radio interference to existing or</p>

		planned primary service radio stations and shall not require protection from harmful radio interference from primary service stations. Protection from radio interference caused by other grants is not guaranteed
Border area between Finland and Russia	<p>The following limits are set to the power flux density (PFD) at the receiving antenna height of 20 m above ground at the border line between Russia and Finland,:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - -105 dBW/MHz/m² in the band 3400-3450 MHz (and -132 dBW/MHz/m² 20 km inside Russia - -115 dBW/MHz/m² in the band 3500-3550 MHz - -132 dBW/MHz/m² in the bands 3450-3500 and 3550-3600 MHz. - shall not exceed -105 dBW/MHz/m² at the receiving antenna height of 20 m <p>The PFD values shall be calculated for 10% of the time (for 3450-3600 MHz for 1% of the time in the area between the border and 60 km of the border).</p>	The PFD produced by a transmitting station does not exceed -139.8 dBW/MHz/m ² at the receiving antenna height of 20 m above ground at the border line between Russia and Finland,;
Border area with Lithuania, Estonia and Belarus	<p>The electromagnetic field value of the MFCN base station shall not exceed 32 dBμV/m/5 MHz at 3 m at the national border.</p> <p>According to ECC Recommendation (15) 01, ITU-R recommendation P.1546-5 at 10% of the time and 50% of the sites shall be used for the calculation.</p>	
Border area between Finland and Estonia	The predicted mean field strength produced by a base station does not exceed 32 dB μ V/m/5 MHz, calculated at 10% of the time, at a height of 3 m above ground at the national border	

As indicated in the table above, both Latvia and Finland have to comply with very strict rules near Russia border area. If the PFD values are above the mentioned levels, a frequency assignment shall be coordinated with the other country. Due to the war in Ukraine, this is not possible.

5 Remote Interference Coordination Frameworks for Cross-border Coordination

In the deployment of 5G networks across cross-border regions, one of the significant challenges is managing radio interference between neighbouring countries. Remote interference, which occurs when wireless signals from one country's network affect the communication quality of neighbouring networks, poses a critical threat to maintaining seamless communication for applications such as Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM).

Interference becomes especially problematic in cross-border regions where frequency reuse across national borders can lead to spectrum overlaps. Without effective coordination mechanisms, the performance of 5G networks can be significantly degraded, causing issues such as dropped connections, high latency, and loss of service quality. Thus, effective remote interference coordination (RIC) frameworks are necessary to mitigate these issues.

5.1 The Need for Interference Coordination in Cross-border Contexts

5G services, particularly those supporting Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) and other CAM applications, demand ultra-low latency and high reliability, making them highly sensitive to interference. Cross-border regions present a unique challenge because radio signals can propagate across national boundaries, leading to co-channel interference when adjacent countries use the same frequency bands for their networks.

Moreover, differences in national spectrum allocation policies and the use of varied network infrastructure intensify the risk of interference in these areas. For instance, while one country might deploy 5G in certain band, another might utilize this band for other services, leading to conflicting signal usage. As 5G networks roll out in increasingly dense environments, such as urban centers near borders, the need for coordination frameworks that can manage interference and ensure spectrum harmony becomes paramount.

5.2 Remote Interference Coordination Frameworks

Remote Interference Coordination (RIC) frameworks are designed to mitigate the risks posed by cross-border interference by coordinating the use of spectrum and network resources between countries. These frameworks rely on several key strategies, including spectrum sharing, coordinated frequency reuse, and the deployment of advanced interference management algorithms.

5.2.1 Spectrum Sharing

One of the primary methods employed in RIC frameworks is spectrum sharing, which involves neighboring countries cooperating to share parts of the radio frequency spectrum in a way that minimizes interference. Spectrum sharing can be done on a static or dynamic basis:

Static spectrum sharing: Countries agree to allocate certain bands exclusively for specific services, thus preventing co-channel interference by separating the usage of those bands. This strategy relies on strict adherence to pre-agreed band allocations and careful planning of base station placements to avoid cross-border signal propagation [23].

Dynamic spectrum sharing: This approach is more flexible, allowing spectrum resources to be shared dynamically based on real-time traffic demands. For instance, dynamic sharing can adjust the frequency use based on the geographical location of active users and network load, reducing the likelihood of interference by adjusting allocations as needed [24].

5.3 Coordinated Frequency Reuse

Coordinated frequency reuse involves designing 5G networks in a way that minimizes the reuse of frequencies near border areas. By coordinating the deployment of cell towers and base stations between

countries, network operators can avoid using the same frequency bands in adjacent areas that are prone to interference. This coordination requires both geographical planning and frequency harmonization, ensuring that the signals from one country do not overlap into another's network coverage areas.

For example, frequency reuse plans can be designed to avoid the simultaneous use of certain bands within specific distances of national borders, reducing the possibility of remote interference. Countries can also implement guard bands—small frequency buffers between actively used bands—to prevent spillover into adjacent channels used by a neighbouring country's network [24].

5.3.1 Interference Management Algorithms

Interference management algorithms play a key role in modern RIC frameworks by allowing networks to dynamically detect and mitigate interference in real-time. These algorithms are often integrated into 5G base stations and core network infrastructure, enabling them to adapt to changes in the radio environment as mobile users move between countries or as network loads shift.

Examples of these algorithms include:

- **Power control algorithms:** These adjust the transmission power of base stations and user devices to limit the range of signals, preventing excessive signal propagation into neighbouring countries' networks.
- **Beamforming techniques:** Massive MIMO (Multiple Input, Multiple Output) antennas and beamforming technologies allow signals to be directed with high precision, minimizing interference in unwanted areas by focusing signal transmission towards desired directions.

Additionally, some advanced frameworks utilize machine learning algorithms that can predict interference patterns based on historical data and network conditions. These predictive models enable networks to proactively adjust their parameters to prevent interference before it occurs, significantly improving the coordination between countries [25].

5.4 The Role of Cross-border Agreements

Effective interference coordination frameworks require the establishment of cross-border agreements between national regulatory bodies and Mobile Network Operators (MNOs). These agreements must address the following key areas:

Spectrum harmonization: Agreeing on common spectrum bands for 5G services across borders can significantly reduce the risk of interference. Harmonization allows for consistent frequency use, minimizing the overlap of signals across national boundaries [26].

Shared infrastructure development: In some cases, cross-border agreements may include provisions for the joint development of network infrastructure, such as shared base stations or multi-national cell towers that serve users in both countries while minimizing interference.

Policy alignment: Regulatory bodies must work together to align their frequency allocation policies, interference mitigation protocols, and network management standards. This ensures that MNOs can operate their networks without risking cross-border signal conflicts [26].

5.5 Challenges in Implementing Remote Interference Coordination

Despite the clear benefits of RIC frameworks, there are several challenges in implementing these systems effectively:

Political and regulatory differences: Countries often have distinct approaches to spectrum management and 5G deployment, making it difficult to establish uniform coordination frameworks. Achieving alignment on spectrum policies can require extensive negotiation between governments and regulatory authorities [5].

Cost and complexity: Deploying and managing advanced RIC frameworks, particularly those that involve dynamic spectrum sharing and interference management algorithms, can be costly. Furthermore, the technical complexity of such systems requires specialized infrastructure and expertise, which may not be readily available in all countries.

Technological limitations: While modern interference management algorithms and beamforming techniques can mitigate many interference issues, there are still limitations to how effectively they can eliminate all interference, particularly in densely populated border regions where spectrum usage is high [26].

5.6 Future Directions and Recommendations

To improve cross-border coordination and reduce the impact of remote interference, the following steps are recommended:

Developing standardized RIC frameworks: International standards organizations like 3GPP and ITU should develop standardized frameworks for interference coordination that can be adopted by countries globally. These frameworks should include guidelines for dynamic spectrum sharing, coordinated frequency reuse, and the use of advanced interference management techniques [5].

Fostering cross-border regulatory collaboration: National regulators need to enhance their collaboration to harmonize spectrum policies and share best practices for interference management. Multi-national regulatory bodies, such as the Radio Spectrum Policy Group (RSPG) in Europe, should play a leading role in facilitating this coordination [26].

Investment in advanced technologies: Governments and MNOs should invest in advanced interference management technologies, including machine learning-based prediction models and massive MIMO systems. These technologies can significantly improve the real-time detection and mitigation of interference in cross-border networks [26].

6 Maritime Trials Results

The 5G-ROUTES project conducted extensive maritime trials to explore the deployment of 5G connectivity across maritime environments, focusing on using multi-hop communication between vessels and onshore networks. These trials were crucial in understanding the challenges and opportunities of providing seamless connectivity over large open water areas by integrating both terrestrial 5G networks and satellite communication systems.

6.1 Concept of Maritime Trials

The primary aim of the maritime trials was to develop a system capable of providing uninterrupted connectivity over large open water areas. The trials focused on improving communication for maritime logistics, real-time data transfer, and live video streaming, thereby enhancing operations and services across maritime transport systems.

The trials leveraged private 5G Standalone (SA) networks installed on vessels, which could communicate with each other and with the onshore public 5G Non-Standalone (NSA) network. The concept of multi-hop functionality allowed vessels to relay data to one another before reaching the onshore network, effectively extending the communication range and ensuring reliable connectivity even in remote maritime environments.

6.2 Maritime Pilot Configurations

Two primary configurations were tested during the trials:

1. Configuration A: In this setup, a larger vessel equipped with both satellite and 5G connectivity acted as a relay for a smaller vessel. The smaller vessel depended on the larger vessel to transmit data to the onshore 5G network.
2. Configuration B: This configuration allowed the smaller vessel to serve as a relay for the larger vessel, thereby extending the coverage of the larger vessel's 5G connection. This setup prioritized the 5G multi-hop connection over the satellite link.

6.3 Use Cases in Maritime Trials

The maritime trials evaluated several specific use cases, demonstrating how 5G can support various maritime applications:

1. Connected Logistics (UC5.1): This use case focused on enabling continuous connectivity for onboard devices and seamless data exchange between vessels and back-end systems. Applications included real-time vehicle monitoring, cybersecurity health reporting, and critical operational data transfer.
2. Live Video Streaming (UC5.2): This trial explored real-time video streaming between ferries and between ferries and onshore networks. It aimed to improve passenger experience and enhance operational control, particularly during vessel manoeuvring and docking.
3. 360° Immersive Multi-User Gaming (UC4.1): Passengers aboard the vessels participated in immersive gaming experiences enabled by low-latency, high-bandwidth 5G networks.

6.4 Results and Performance Assessment

The trials were conducted in three stages: lab tests, campus-area tests, and open-sea trials. The key performance indicators focused on latency, throughput, and service availability under real-world conditions, including moving vessels and fluctuating environmental factors. The tests, performed in terrestrial environments, are reported in D1.13.

Key findings from the trials include:

1. **Latency and Uplink Performance:** Maintaining low latency over multi-hop configurations proved challenging. In the lab tests, each hop added roughly 10 ms extra delay. The latency when using satellite connection instead of terrestrial increases the RTT latency to about 140-200 ms especially when switching between satellite and terrestrial 5G connections. The asymmetric Uplink/Downlink ratio constraints the performance, and the weakest link limits the overall system performance, especially in uplink direction.
2. **Multi-Hop Bottlenecks:** in Configuration A, the communication of the vessel, which is farthest from the shore, depends on the performances of the multi-hop link to the vessel, closer to the shore. If this link is weakened or lost, the vessel farther from the shore cannot anymore exchange data.
3. **Service Continuity:** Configuration B addressed the limitations of Configuration A by dynamically relaying traffic between vessels. This resulted in more reliable service continuity, even during disruptions in direct 5G connections between the vessels.

6.5 Issues and Challenges

Several technical and operational challenges emerged during the maritime trials:

1. **Bandwidth Limitations:** for performing the trials, a bandwidth of 100 MHz (40/60) would be ideal. 30 MHz from one MNO in the n78 band proved to be insufficient. To avoid bottlenecks, 40 MHz for the one-hop network and 20 MHz for the two-hop network is needed. and 20 MHz for one-hop network results in a significant decrease in uplink performance. The uplink performance of multi-hop is degraded when the public 5G coverage, used for the link between vessel and shore, is weak.
2. **Interference and Coverage:** The multi-hop configuration caused interference between the private networks installed on the vessels, especially when they operated in close proximity. When using directional antennas, the antenna of the vessels have to be directed towards each other. Coverage provided by the onshore public network varied due to geographical factors, and due to multiple handovers between on-shore cells.
3. **Link Management:** Managing the transition between satellite and terrestrial 5G connections proved to be a critical issue. The switch delay from public 5G network to OneWeb was around 2.2 seconds. The link management function parameters need further investigation.
4. **Environmental Factors:** Weather conditions, vessel movement, and the availability of both satellite and terrestrial networks introduced variability in the performance results.
5. **Synchronisation of base stations.** The base station started executing automatically a cell survey during vessel movement due to a large GNSS phase error, which caused the system to be unavailable for about half an hour. This was solved together with the base station manufacturer, by allowing the GNSS receiver of the gNB to tolerate a better phase error.
6. **Processes for approval of floating base stations** have to be developed. Current spectrum approval procedures are based on fixed base station positions. The procedures should include new applications, in which base stations are moving. This would benefit not only the maritime multi-hop system, but also e.g. innovative use cases with airborne base stations.

7. Frequency management and coordination of different networks, especially when floating networks are in use. In the multi-hop experiments, there were issues when the private networks in the participating vessels were in the same frequency band. In the experiment the issue was solved by assigning different frequency bands to the vessels, which is not an efficient use of the frequency spectrum nor a scalable solution. GSMA is the standardisation organisation, to which dynamic frequency allocation should be proposed.
8. Absence of mIAB interfaces in multi-hop. The traffic traverses through multiple RANs and 5G Cores, so each hop increases RTT latency by 10–13 ms. IAB or a similar concept is hence absolutely needed. Multi-hop should be handled on the L2 MAC, or with better radio controllability on the L3 (RLC). Core network involvement in RL (radio link) management needs to be excluded due to delays that would render the solution useless rather quickly.

7 Conclusions

The 5G-ROUTES project has made significant strides in advancing our understanding of Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) and its integration with 5G technology. This chapter synthesizes the key findings, contributions, and future directions identified throughout our research, building upon the foundation laid in our initial report (D5.9) and incorporating new insights from our extensive trials and analyses.

The maritime trials conducted by 5G-ROUTES have opened new avenues for extending CAM services to maritime environments. The project demonstrated the potential of multi-hop communication in extending network coverage over large open water areas, while also highlighting challenges in maintaining low latency and managing bandwidth limitations in maritime settings.

1. Gap Analysis and Proposed Solutions:
 - Proposal: Development of ETSI Release 2 messages, including Collective Perception Messages (CPM) and Maneuver Coordination Messages (MCM)
 - Proposal: Enhancement of security-related standardisation for CAM, focusing on end-to-end security in cross-border scenarios
2. Spectrum Allocation Recommendations:
 - Proposal: Implementation of dynamic spectrum access technologies, particularly in urban areas
 - Proposal: Development of coverage-based spectrum allocation metrics focused on road and rail infrastructure
3. Cross-Border Operations:
 - Proposal: Standardisation of 5G cross-border roaming protocols, addressing both inter-MNO and multi-MNO scenarios
 - Proposal: Establishment of clear protocols for spectrum use in border areas to ensure seamless transitions for CAM services

The spectrum allocation recommendations aim to create a flexible and efficient spectrum environment that can support the diverse needs of CAM services across the EU, including maritime applications. The proposal for dynamic spectrum access technologies is particularly crucial for optimizing spectrum use in congested urban areas and adaptable maritime environments.

The findings from the trials will inform future standardisation efforts, particularly in areas related to maritime 5G applications, multi-hop communications, and the integration of terrestrial and satellite networks. Identified standardisation needs include:

- Driving standardization forward in 3GPP. There needs to be a own network function or functionality specified for multi-hop functionality.
- There needs to be at least European wide mechanism that allows automatic frequency management for vessels to use private network onboard and utilizing multi-hop functionality.

Effective remote interference coordination frameworks are critical to ensuring seamless 5G communication in cross-border regions. By leveraging spectrum sharing, coordinated frequency reuse, and interference management algorithms, countries can reduce the risk of interference and ensure that 5G services maintain the reliability and performance required for applications such as CAM. However, implementing these frameworks requires significant cross-border collaboration, technological investment, and regulatory alignment. As 5G continues to evolve, the development of standardized RIC frameworks will be essential for supporting the next generation of mobile connectivity.

8 References

- [1] D1.1, “Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0,” 5G-ROUTES.
- [2] 5GPPP, “5G Trials for Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility along European 5G Cross-Border Corridors,” 2020.
- [3] 802.11p, “Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments,” IEEE , 2010.
- [4] 802.11bd, “Evolution of Radio Access Technologies for V2X Communications,” IEEE , 2019.
- [5] TS 23.501, System Architecture for the 5G System, 3GPP, 2018.
- [6] EN 302 665, “Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Communications Architecture,” ETSI, 2010.
- [7] UIC, A Guide to standardisation, “How IRSs are developed and where they fit in the world of the standardisation,” 2019.
- [8] European Commission, “Rolling Plan for ICT standardisation 2020,” 2020.
- [9] ETSI TR 102 962, “Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Framework for Public Mobile Networks in Cooperative ITS (C-ITS),” 2012.
- [10] CONCORDA, “Connected Corridor for Driving Automation,” [Online]. Available: <https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/connected-corridor-driving-automation#tab-funding>.
- [11] CONVERGE, “CarbON Valorisation in Energy-efficient Green fuels,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.converge-h2020.eu/>.
- [12] TR 21186-2, “Cooperative intelligent transport systems (C-ITS) — Guidelines on the usage of standards — Part 2: Hybrid communications,” ISO, 2021.
- [13] TR 103 630, “Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Security; Pre-standardization Study on ITS Facility Layer Security for C-ITS Communication Using Cellular Uu Interface,” ETSI , 2020.
- [14] GS MEC 030, “ Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC); V2X Information Service API,” ETSI , 2020.
- [15] TS 22.186 , “Service requirements for enhanced V2X scenarios; 2017,” 3GPP , 2017.
- [16] TS 23.287, “Architecture enhancements for 5G System (5GS) to support Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) services,” 3GPP, 2020.
- [17] TS 22.261, “Service requirements for the 5G system,” 3GPP, 2020.
- [18] ITU, “WRC-19 Additional frequency bands for 5G,” 2020. [Online]. Available: [8] <https://www.itu.int/en/myitu/News/2020/01/24/14/40/WRC19-identifies-additional-frequency-bands-for-5G#:~:text=While%20identifying%20the%20of%20frequency%20bands,passive%20services%20in%20adjacent%20bands>.
- [19] COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING DECISION, “Harmonised use of radio spectrum in the 5 875-5 935 MHz frequency band for safety-related applications of intelligent transport systems (ITS),” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/>.
- [20] “Basements and crawl spaces. (2002, June 23),” Retrieved from <http://www.hud.gov/offices/hsg/sfh/ref/sfhp1-25.cfm>, 2002.
- [21] TR 22.886, “Study on enhancement of 3GPP Support for 5G V2X Services,” 3GPP, 2020.
- [22] TR 102 638 , “Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Vehicular Communications; Basic Set of Applications; Definitions,” ETSI, 2009.
- [23] <https://jwcn-eurasipjournals.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s13638-021-01926-2>
- [24] https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_tr/138900_138999/138912/14.01.00_60/tr_138912v140100p.pdf
- [25] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1389128623006047>
- [26] https://radio-spectrum-policy-group.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-10/RSPG23-04ofinal-RSPG_Opinion_on_5G_developments_and_6G_spectrum_needs.pdf